

Complexation equilibria of ciprofloxacin with proton and metal ions in aqueous-organic mixtures

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Abstract : The proton-ligand stability constants ($\log K_1^H$, $\log K_2^H$) of ciprofloxacin (CIP) and its metal-ligand stability constants ($\log K_1$) in aqueous, acetonitrile-water, alcohol-water, DMSO-water and 1,4-dioxan-water (25 : 75 and 50 : 50% v/v) mixtures have been determined potentiometrically at 25 ± 0.1 °C and 0.1 mol dm^{-3} (NaCl) ionic strength. Ciprofloxacin formed 1 : 1 (M : L) complexes with VO^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Ni^{II} , Mn^{II} and Co^{II} . In general, the values of $\log K_1$ follow Irving-Williams stability order in each solvent system.

Keywords : Ciprofloxacin, metal ions, stability constant, ionization constant.

Introduction

Ciprofloxacin [1-cyclopropyl-6-fluoro-1,4-dihydro-4-oxo-7-(piperazinyl)-quinolone-3-carboxylic acid] is a member of the fluoroquinolone class of synthetic antimicrobial agents that has broad spectrum of activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative organisms and is widely used in human and veterinary medicines¹. Modified pharmacological and toxicological properties of these drugs in the form of metallic complexes have been studied². Some reports were published on the stability constants of ciprofloxacin complexes with metal ions in aqueous medium³. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants of ciprofloxacin with some transition metal ions in aqueous-organic mixtures have been carried out. The endeavor of the present investigation is : (i) determination of proton-ligand and (ii) metal-ligand stability constants of ciprofloxacin in aqueous and aqueous-organic systems.

Results and discussion

Proton-ligand stability constants : Ciprofloxacin (1) has two potentially ionizable functional groups. It titrates as biprotic acid and offers two well separated buffer regions in the pH range (3.0–10.0) due to successive deprotonation of -COOH and protonated piperazinyl 4'- NH_2^+ moieties. Since -COOH group is a stronger acid than the protonated piperazinyl group, the first ionization constant $\log K_2^H$ corresponds to the dissociation of a proton from the 3-carboxylic group and $\log K_1^H$ corres-

ponds to the dissociation of proton from protonated nitrogen atom in piperazinyl group⁴.

(1)

In case of ciprofloxacin, the experimentally reported values are $\log K_2^H$ 6.2 and $\log K_1^H$ 8.8 while those estimated theoretically by the SPARC computer program are 5.46 and 7.67 respectively. The present values of the proton-ligand stability constants in different aqueous-organic mixtures are given in Table 1.

The slight variations in the present $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ values (Table 1) in aqueous medium compared to literature values may be due to the different ionic strength (0.2 M KCl) reported in data published earlier³. Highest $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ values were observed in acetonitrile-water while lowest in DMSO-water. Co-solvent (acetonitrile, alcohol, DMSO and 1,4-dioxan in the present case) influences the complexation equilibria in solution due to change in dielectric constant of the medium⁵. Greater $\log K_2^H$ was observed in each aqueous-organic

mixture as compared to water, suggesting, thereby, less acidic character in mixed solvents. This can be explained on the basis of lower dielectric constant of dioxan-H₂O system [60.56 (25 : 75); 41.11 (50 : 50)], acetonitrile-H₂O system [69.37 (25 : 75); 58.75 (50 : 50)], DMSO-water [71.80 (25 : 75); 63.60 (50 : 50)], alcohol-water [66.07 (25 : 75); 52.15 (50 : 50)] as compared to water only having dielectric constant 78.5, and proton solvation properties of the media.

Table 1. Proton-ligand stability constant of ciprofloxacin in aqueous and aqueous-organic mixtures at 25 °C and ionic strength of 0.1 M NaCl

Solvent composition (% v/v)	log K_2^H	log K_1^H
Water	5.796	8.044
Acetonitrile (25)	6.430	8.287
Acetonitrile (50)	6.883	8.805
Alcohol (25)	6.340	8.078
Alcohol (50)	6.232	7.686
DMSO (25)	5.957	7.642
DMSO (50)	6.159	7.003
1,4-Dioxan (25)	6.110	7.720
1,4-Dioxan (50)	6.724	7.814

Metal-ligand stability constants : The stability constant data (log K_1) for metal-CIP complexes reported in Table 2 show stability trend in aqueous-organic medium. In case of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} the observed trends in different aqueous-organic mixtures, in general, are in accordance with Irving-Williams order of stability. The different stability trends in various solvent mixtures indicate the varying extent of solvation of metal ions and ciprofloxacin in solution⁶.

Experimental

Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride (C₁₇H₁₈FN₃O₃·HCl, formula mass = 367.84) was procured from MP Biochemicals, Inc. and its 0.01 M solution was prepared in double glass distilled water. All other reagents used were of A.R. grade. Metal salt solutions were prepared in double glass distilled water.

pH-meter and accessories : A Digital pH meter, Model 5652 A (Electronic Corporation of India Limited) with glass and calomel electrodes assembly, reading up to 0.01 units was used for measuring the pH of solutions prepared. Before starting the experiment, the pH meter was standardized with the help of buffer solutions of pH 4.0, 7.0 and 9.2.

Titration details : Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration tech-

Table 2. Metal-ligand stability constant of ciprofloxacin in aqueous and aqueous-organic mixtures at 25 °C and ionic strength of 0.1 M NaCl

Solvent composition (% v/v)	log K_1					
	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Co ^{II}	VO ^{II}	Mn ^{II}	Ni ^{II}
Water	8.88	6.20	6.46	10.42	-	-
Acetonitrile (25)	10.20	6.32	6.33	10.55	5.72	7.47
Acetonitrile (50)	9.12	6.52	-	9.02	5.01	6.30
Alcohol (25)	10.09	6.64	6.09	-	5.53	6.71
Alcohol (50)	8.88	5.69	5.24	8.19	-	6.02
DMSO (25)	9.29	6.02	-	9.62	5.40	6.60
DMSO (50)	7.96	4.95	-	7.15	5.47	5.60
1,4-Dioxan (25)	8.61	5.79	5.79	9.21	5.01	6.20
1,4-Dioxan (50)	8.77	5.50	-	10.18	5.39	5.85

nique as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁷ was used for potentiometric determination of proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants. The following solutions were titrated against standard carbonate free 0.1 N NaOH in aqueous as well as in aqueous-organic mixtures [acetonitrile-water, alcohol-water, DMSO-water and 1,4-dioxan-water, each 25 : 75 and 50 : 50% v/v];

(i) 1×10^{-2} M HCl, (ii) [(i) + 2.5×10^{-3} M ligand], and (iii) [(ii) + 5×10^{-4} M metal ion solution].

The ionic strength (0.1 M) was adjusted by adding calculated amount of 1.0 M NaCl and the total initial volume of the solution were kept 20 ml by adding appropriate quantity of double distilled water and organic solvents. The pH meter readings in aqueous-organic mixtures were corrected⁸.

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